

I.FAST

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this work package is to design and build an industrial prototype of the LHC klystron -TH2167- klystron reaching 70% efficiency in collaboration with THALES. This report describes the status, the progress made and the next steps.

I.FAST Consortium, 2022

For more information on I.FAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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1. Introduction

The scope of this collaboration between CERN and THALES is to develop and supply a high-efficiency TH2167HE klystron prototype for LHC. In order to control the costs, the choice was made to retrofit the existing LHC klystrons, TH2167, with the aim of reusing some components (e.g. solenoid).

The project splits into two phases as shown in the following figure. The main milestones are:

- Kick off meeting, which took place early September 2021
- The preliminary design report, which took place in December 2021
- The design report, which is foreseen mid-2022. This is the start of the construction phase
- The factory acceptance test (FAT), which is expected during Spring 2023

Figure 1: TH2167 towards TH2167HE

2. Execution schedule, status and progress

The kick-off meeting officially launched the project (although preliminary work had already started) early in September. CERN and THALES engaged into the first phase of the program and froze the main parameters of the new klystron.

The first nine months phase includes the design activities and is marked by two design reviews. The Project Design Review (“PDR”) took place early January. The detailed simulation work was presented and discussed. Both parties validated the first assembly drawing of the new RF structure and an internal progress report was produced. The full 3D PIC simulated performance expected from the TH2167HE is quite satisfactory in terms of RF power, stability, bandwidth and efficiency.

Figure 2: The TH2167HE RF body

Figure 3: 3D PIC full tube (cathode + solenoid + RF circuit + collector) simulations

The magnetic profile of the klystron was optimized in order to reduce the required coil current –and therefore dissipated heat-, optimize the power distribution in the collector and avoid backscattered electrons on the tube. As shown in figure 3, the result is satisfactory: no modulation of the output power is observed and the operating point of the klystron is safe with saturation at 60W drive power. The collector geometry is optimized to reduce the power density across the collector surface and the output cavity redesign to cope with the increased output RF power.

Figure 4: magnetic field profile of the TH2167HE

Figure 5: saturation curve of the TH2167HE

All key pragmatic issues like mechanical or electrical interface were addressed in order to make sure the new design is fully plug and play with the existing TH2167. Figure 4 shows the example of the new hydraulic inlet/outlet positioning.

Figure 6: the hydraulic inlet/outlet positioning

3. Conclusion and Future Plans

The development of the TH2167HE klystron prototype for LHC is ongoing according to plan and is now heading towards the start of the construction phase which shall start during the summer. The overall project schedule is shown in figure 7.

In the meantime the RF design will be reconfirmed and the detailed thermal simulations and mechanical design of the assembly completed and validated.

Figure 7: project schedule